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Overview

Android application Lightvalues LV¹ for calculating *aperture values* Av corresponding to *light values*² by *shifting* the time value $Tv = s^{-1}$ or arithmetic *ISO* speed value S in steps k according to the common classification (s. Fig. 1), where

$$Tv_{n-k} = Tv_n \cdot 2^k, \quad S_{n+k} = S_n \cdot \sqrt{2}^k, \quad (1)$$

$$Tv_{n+k} = \frac{Tv_n}{2^k}, \quad S_{n-k} = \frac{S_n}{\sqrt{2}^k} \quad (2)$$

and

$$Av_{(Tv_n)} = Av_{(Tv_{n+k})} \cdot \sqrt{2}^k = \frac{Av_{(Tv_{n-k})}}{\sqrt{2}^k}, \quad (3)$$

$$Av_{(S_n)} = Av_{(S_{n-k})} \cdot \sqrt{2}^k = \frac{Av_{(S_{n+k})}}{\sqrt{2}^k}. \quad (4)$$

Therefore Av is calculated from Tv or S as

$$Av_{Tv} = Av_{Tv_0} \cdot a_{Tv}, \quad Av_S = Av_{S_0} \cdot a_S \quad (5)$$

with

$$a_{Tv} = 2^{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \log_2 \frac{Tv_0}{Tv}} = e^{\frac{1}{2} \frac{\log(Tv_0)}{Tv}}, \quad (6)$$

$$a_S = 2^{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \log_2 \frac{S}{S_0}} = e^{\frac{1}{2} \frac{\log S}{S_0}}. \quad (7)$$

The shutter speed is set in the range between $Tv = 32000$ and 2 hours, $Tv = 0.00013\bar{8}$, aperture ranges from $Av = 0.5$ to $Av = 152$ and speed S is set to range between *ISO* 0.4 and *ISO* 102400. On aperture, shutter speed and exposure see e.g. Roberts (1995), Beaver (2018), Bernacki (2020) and Simon et al. (2022).

Logarithmic speed S° (s. Allbright, 1991) is transformed from arithmetic speed S by

$$S^\circ = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(S) + 1 = \frac{10 \cdot \log(S)}{\log(10)} + 1, \quad (8)$$

$$S = 10^{\frac{S^\circ - 1}{10}}. \quad (9)$$

¹ <https://github.com/Schrausser/LV>

² Light level for incident or reflected light on a logarithmic scale.

The exposure value Ev is calculated from Tv and Av , where

$$Ev = \log_2 \frac{Av^2}{Tv^{-1}} = \frac{\log(Tv \cdot Av^2)}{\log(2)}, Tv = \frac{2^{Ev}}{Av^2}, Av = \frac{\sqrt{2^{Ev} \cdot Tv}}{Tv}. \quad (10)$$

The total luminous flux or illuminance E_V in lux lx , where $lx = \frac{lm}{m^2}$ results from Ev and S by

$$E_V = 250 \cdot \frac{2^{Ev}}{S}. \quad (11)$$

For logarithmic functions in general see e.g. Marsden & Weinstein (1985), Howie (2001) and Sobot (2021).

Presets for time and aperture combinations at $ISO\ 100/21^\circ$ (8) are given (s. Tab. 1), with aperture values Av are rounded to one decimal place. Custom *time-aperture-ISO* combinations for exposure values Ev (10) or illuminance E_V (11) can be achieved by shifting Av itself (s. Fig. 1).

Table 1. Exposure presets for Tv , Av and Ev (10) at $ISO\ 100/21^\circ$ by condition *cond*.

<i>cond</i>	Tv	Av	Ev
<i>Sun</i>	125	11	14
<i>Cloud</i>	125	8	13
<i>Overcast</i>	60	5.6	11
<i>Dawn</i>	15	4	8
<i>Indoors</i>	15	2.8	7

In addition, direct calculations (5) of aperture Av from shutter speed Tv (6) and S (7) can be performed (c.f. Schrausser, 2025). This should be used when shutter speeds outside the usual steps (1) (2) are present or when only *one* shutter speed is available, as in the case of the so-called mechanical *emergency* shutter speed (s. Tab. 2).

Table 2. Av for Tv (5) (6) at $ISO\ 100/21^\circ$ and $ISO\ 400/27^\circ$ with Ev (10) by condition *cond*.

<i>cond</i>	Tv				Ev
	250	100	60	45	
<i>ISO 100/21°</i>					
<i>Sun</i>	7.8	12.3	15.9	18.3	13.9
<i>Cloud</i>	5.7	9.0	11.6	13.3	13.0
<i>Overcast</i>	2.8	4.3	5.6	6.5	10.9
<i>Dawn</i>	1.0	1.6	2.0	2.3	7.9
<i>Indoors</i>	0.7	1.1	1.4	1.6	6.9
<i>ISO 400/27°</i>					
<i>Sun</i>	15.6	24.6	32.0	36.7	15.9
<i>Cloud</i>	11.4	18.0	23.2	26.6	15.0
<i>Overcast</i>	5.6	8.6	11.2	13.0	12.9
<i>Dawn</i>	2.0	3.1	4.0	4.6	9.9
<i>Indoors</i>	1.4	2.2	2.8	3.2	8.9

Further manuals or introductory literature on photography are given by e.g. Hedgecoe (1977, 2009) and Jacobson et al. (2000), see also Kenneth Mees (1931), Cannon & Hunt (1981), Hitchcock (1989), Current et al. (2000), Friedman & Ross (2003) or Pavlidis (2022).

Figure 1. Screenshots from LV Application.

Source

```

! ////////////////////////////////////////
! // LV Lightvalues
! // Exposure calculator
! // by Dietmar G. Schrausser © 2025
! //
_name$="LV"
_ver$="3.8.2"
_CONSOLE.TITLE _name$
_INCLUDE strg.inc
_INCLUDE lv.inc
_GOSUB values
sw=-3
insw=1                                     % // color switch //
tv=10                                       % // input switch //
av=18
av1=18
iso=18:iso$="100"
!
m1:
IF sw=1 :r=255:g=255:b=255:ENDIF
IF sw=0 :r=0 :g=0 :b=0 :ENDIF
IF sw=-1:r=80 :g=30 :b=30 :ENDIF
IF sw=-2:r=30 :g=80 :b=30 :ENDIF
IF sw=-3:r=80 :g=90 :b=180:ENDIF
GR.OPEN 255,r,g,b,0,1
GR.SCREEN sx,sy
dy=sy/3/4
txz0=sx/10
txz1=sx/2.5
txz2=sx/3.5
GR.TEXT.BOLD 1
IF insw=1 THEN GOSUB inpt
!
DO
!
insw=1
GOSUB col
!                                     % // AV shift //
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH swavp,0,sy/3,sx/3,sy*2/3
IF swavp=1
IF av>1:av=av-1:rav=av:rtv=tv:ENDIF
GOSUB subl

```

```

ENDIF
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH swavm,sx*2/3,sy/3,sx,sy*2/3
IF swavm=1
  IF av<36:av=av+1:rav=av:rtv=tv:ENDIF
  GOSUB subl
ENDIF
!
! % // menue //
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH swin,sx/3,sy/3,sx*2/3,sy*2/3
IF swin=1
  GOSUB inpt:GR.CLS
ENDIF
!
! % // TV shift //
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH swtvp,0,0,sx/3,sy/3
IF swtvp=1
  IF tv>1:tv=tv-1:av=av-2:ENDIF
  GOSUB subl
ENDIF
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH swtvm,sx*2/3,0,sx,sy/3
IF swtvm=1
  IF tv<31:tv=tv+1:av=av+2:ENDIF
  GOSUB subl
ENDIF
!
! % // iso shift //
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH swisop,sx*2/3,sy*2/3,sx,sy
IF swisop=1
  IF iso<39:iso=iso+1
    av=av+1
    GOSUB subl
  ENDIF
ENDIF
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH swisom,0,sy*2/3,sx/3,sy
IF swisom=1
  IF iso>1:iso=iso-1
    av=av-1
    GOSUB subl
  ENDIF
ENDIF
!
! % // text TV //
iso$=iso$[iso]
IF sw>-1
  IF tv=rtv THEN GR.COLOR 255,255/2,0,0,1
ENDIF
IF tv<1 THEN GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx/2,sy/3-dy,Tv$[1]
IF tv>31 THEN GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx/2,sy/3-dy,Tv$[29]
IF tv>0 & tv<32
  GR.TEXT.SIZE txz0
  GR.TEXT.ALIGN 1
  GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,0,dy,"Tv"
  IF tv<17
    GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,0,sy*3/12," 1/"
  ENDIF
  GR.TEXT.SIZE txz2
  GR.TEXT.ALIGN 2
  GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx/2,sy/3-dy,Tv$[tv]
ENDIF
GOSUB col
!
! % // text AV //
IF sw>-1
  IF rav=av THEN GR.COLOR 255,255/2,0,0,1
ENDIF
IF av<1 THEN GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx/2,sy*2/3-dy,Av$[1]
IF av>36 THEN GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx/2,sy*2/3-dy,Av$[36]
IF av>0 & av<37
  av1=av
  GR.TEXT.SIZE txz0
  GR.TEXT.ALIGN 1
  GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,0,sy/2+dy/2,"Av"
  GR.TEXT.SIZE txz1
  GR.TEXT.ALIGN 2
  GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx/2,sy*2/3-dy,Av$[av1]
ENDIF
GOSUB col
!
! % // text iso //
GR.TEXT.SIZE txz0
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 1
GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,0,sy-dy/3,"ISO"
GR.TEXT.SIZE txz2
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 2
GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx/2,sy-dy,iso$

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!
GR.BOUNDED.TOUCH t1,sx/3,sy*2/3,sx*2/3,sy
IF t1
  insw=0
  sw=sw+1:IF sw=2 THEN sw=-3
  GR.CLOSE:GOTO m1
ENDIF
!
GR.TEXT.SIZE txz0
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 3
IF dlg<>6
  GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx,sy/20,lv$[dlg]
ELSE
  IF tv<31 & av1<35 & tv>1 & av>1 & iso>1 & iso<39
    GOSUB v0: GOSUB EV
  ENDIF
  GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx,sy/20,ev$+" Ev"
  GOSUB E_V
  GR.TEXT.SIZE sx/15
  GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx,sy-sy/100,e_v$+" lx"
ENDIF
GOSUB ln
GR.RENDER
!
UNTIL 0
!
ONERROR:
ONBACKKEY:
GOSUB fin
END
!
! // sub ////////////////////////////////////////
!
values:
ARRAY.LOAD tv$[], "+",
"32000","16000","8000","4000","2000","1000","500","250","125","60","30","15","8","4",
"2","1"+i$,"2"+i$,"4"+i$,"8"+i$,"15"+i$,"30"+i$,"1'", "2'", "4'", "8'", "15'", "30'", "1h",
"2h", "- "
ARRAY.LOAD av$[], "-
", "0.5","0.6","0.7","0.8","1.0","1.2","1.4","1.7","2.0","2.4","2.8","3.4","4.0","4.8",
"5.6","6.7","8.0","9.5","11","13.5","16","19","22","27","32","38","44","54","64","76",
"88","108","128","152","+ "
ARRAY.LOAD iso$[], "-
", "0.4","0.6","0.8","1.1","1.5","2.2","3","4.4","6","8.8","12.5","18","25","35","50",
"71","100","141","200","283","400","566","800","1131","1600","2263","3200","4526","64",
"00","9051","12800","18102","25600","36204","51200","72408","102400","+ "
RETURN
!
col:
IF sw=1 THEN GR.COLOR 255,30 ,30 ,30 ,1
IF sw=0 THEN GR.COLOR 255,180,180,180,1
IF sw=-1 THEN GR.COLOR 255,255,30 ,30 ,1
IF sw=-2 THEN GR.COLOR 255,30 ,255,30 ,1
IF sw=-3 THEN GR.COLOR 255,240,240,240,1
RETURN
!
ln:
GR.LINE l1,0,sy*1/3,sx,sy*1/3
GR.LINE l2,0,sy*2/3,sx,sy*2/3
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 1
GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,0,sy*1/6," -"
GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,0,sy*5/6," -"
GR.TEXT.ALIGN 3
GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx,sy*1/6,"+ "
GR.TEXT.DRAW tx,sx,sy*5/6,"+ "
RETURN
!
sub1:
PAUSE 100:GR.CLS
RETURN
!
inpt:
ARRAY.LOAD lv$[],m1$+" Sun",m2$+" Cloud",m3$+" Overcast",m4$+" Dawn",m5$+"
Indoors",m6$+" EV",m7$+" Calculate",_ex$+" Exit"
DIALOG.SELECT dlg, lv$[],_name$+" "+_ver$+" - ISO@100 ..."
IF dlg=5:tv=13:av=12:iso=18:ENDIF
IF dlg=4:tv=13:av=14:iso=18:ENDIF
IF dlg=3:tv=11:av=16:iso=18:ENDIF
IF dlg=2:tv=10:av=18:iso=18:ENDIF

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```

IF dlg=1:tv=10:av=20:iso=18:ENDIF
IF dlg=7
  IF tv<31 & av1<35 & tv>1 & av>1 & iso>1 & iso<39
    GOSUB v0
    GOSUB calc
  ENDIF
ENDIF
IF dlg=8:GOSUB fin:END:ENDIF
rtv=tv
rav=av
RETURN
!
calc:
GOSUB EV:GOSUB E_V
ARRAY.LOAD calc$[],"Tv= 1/"+tv0$+" (" +tv1$+" )s","Av= "+av0$,"ISO=
"+iso0$+"/"+"din$+"°","Ev: "+ev$,e_v$+" lx","Ok"
DIALOG.SELECT dlg2, calc$[],m7$+" Calculate..."
IF dlg2=1
  INPUT "Tv=...",tv01,VAL(tv0$)
  GOSUB AvTv
  GOTO calc
ENDIF
IF dlg2=2
  INPUT "Av=...",av01,VAL(av0$)
  av0$=STR$(av01)
  tv01=VAL(tv0$)
  GOSUB AvTv
  GOTO calc
ENDIF
IF dlg2=3
  INPUT "ISO=...",iso01,VAL(iso0$)
  GOSUB Aviso
  GOTO calc
ENDIF
IF dlg2=6 THEN GOTO inpt
RETURN
!
v0:
IF tv<17 % // conversions //
  tv0$=Tv$(tv) % // Tv < 1sec //
  tv1$=STR$(ROUND(1/VAL(tv0$),5))
ENDIF
IF tv>16 % // Tv >= 1sec //
  SW.BEGIN tv
  SW.CASE 17:tv0$="1" :tv1$="1" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 18:tv0$="0.5" :tv1$="2" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 19:tv0$="0.25" :tv1$="4" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 20:tv0$="0.125" :tv1$="8" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 21:tv0$="0.0667" :tv1$="15" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 22:tv0$="0.0333" :tv1$="30" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 23:tv0$="0.0167" :tv1$="60" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 24:tv0$="0.0083" :tv1$="120" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 25:tv0$="0.0042" :tv1$="240" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 26:tv0$="0.0021" :tv1$="480" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 27:tv0$="0.0011" :tv1$="900" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 28:tv0$="0.00056" :tv1$="1800" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 29:tv0$="0.00028" :tv1$="3600" :SW.BREAK
  SW.CASE 30:tv0$="0.00014" :tv1$="7200" :SW.BREAK
  SW.END
ENDIF
av0$=Av$(av1)
iso0$=iso$
din$=INT$(INT(10*LOG10(VAL(iso0$))+1)) % // DIN //
RETURN
!
AvTv: % // calc Av Tv //
av0$=STR$(VAL(av0$)*EXP((0.5*LOG(VAL(tv0$)/tv01))))
av0$=STR$(ROUND(VAL(av0$),2))
tv0$=STR$(tv01)
tv1$=STR$(ROUND(1/tv01,5))
RETURN
!
Aviso: % // calc Av iso //
av0$=STR$(VAL(av0$)*EXP((0.5*LOG(iso01/VAL(iso0$))))
av0$=STR$(ROUND(VAL(av0$),2))
iso0$=STR$(iso01)
din$=STR$(ROUND(10*LOG10(iso01)+1,1))
RETURN
!

```

```

EV:                                     % // calc Ev      //
ev$=STR$(ROUND(1/LOG(2)*LOG((VAL(av0$))^2/(VAL(tv0$))^-1),2))
RETURN
!
E_V:                                     % // calc E_V     //
e_v$=STR$(ROUND(250*(2^VAL(ev$)/VAL(ISO0$)),2))
RETURN
!
fin:
PRINT _name$+" Lightvalues "+_ver$
PRINT "Copyright "+_cr$+" 2025 by Dietmar Gerald Schrausser"
PRINT "https://github.com/Schrausser/LV"
PRINT "DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16502602"
RETURN
! // END //
! //

```

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